

THEORETICAL BASICS OF WORKING ON TEXT IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL READING LESSONS

Kuchkarova Shakarjan Azimboy daughter

Urgench State University Foundation doctoral student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8313995>

Annotation: The article reflects on the rapid development of Science, Technology and technology, the rapid growth of culture, art and literature on the mental and mental maturation of children. It assumes the use of new methods and techniques in the field of education, in particular, the widespread use of the types of work that cultivate students' independent creative thinking skills and speech. Work on speech cultivation is diverse. The teacher should assist students in acquiring knowledge, skills and qualifications related to speech in his native language, and teach them to skillfully use the skills acquired in practice.

Keywords: speech cultivation, work on the text, oral and written speech, communication, word meaning, speech.

Mother tongue education in primary classes serves to expand children's contemplative activities, to be able to think freely, to understand other people's opinions, to be able to articulate their thoughts fluently orally and in writing, to develop skills and qualifications to be able to communicate freely with members of society. In this regard, the education of the native language is considered not as a teaching subject, but as an educational process that organizes the entire educational system.

Since one of the basic principles of the "native language program" is also aimed at the development of speech, in order to successfully solve this task, each teacher must, firstly, clearly imagine the content of work on speech culture, that is, specific speech skills that should be given to the student, and secondly, the methods of organizing education, that is, the corresponding types of exercises. In other words, when acquiring one or another grammatical-orthographic qualification, one must know what to teach from the point of view of speech and how to do it.

As noted, reading artistic texts included in the textbooks of the elementary grade "reading book" also contributes to the formation of students' spirituality, expanding their imagination and raising their emotions. In the process, their speech is also enriched with new words and phrases.

According to Methodist-scholars, reading is a manifestation of speech activity, which consists in the identification, active processing and

understanding of information from the text. True, reading the text is the identification of the information expressed in it. However, this is not his own description. Because hearing speech in general, understanding that it is narrated or that someone reads aloud, is also information recognition, active processing, understanding. So, an important feature of reading is not in obtaining information, but in what basis the acquisition of information was carried out. The reading process is closely related to the text. Even the best reader will begin to read slowly with difficulty if faced with a difficult word or complex text.

Many scholars, linguists and literary scholars, Methodists and teachers have expressed their views on the theoretical foundations, methods of speech and its cultivation in the elementary grades.

N. The bekniyazova monograph [6], on the other hand, studied the theoretical, practical, linguomethodic foundations of teaching text creation to students in the native language classes of primary classes, expressed valuable ideas about the organizational and lexical-grammatical features of the internal structure of the text, the system of exercises in teaching text creation, teaching the improvement of the structured text.

The research work of Safo Matchanov [4] shows the methods of organizing independent work by teaching students to work on the text. In it, the types of text, their differences from each other and the stages of work on the text are covered by the example of the product of many years of scientific research by the author.

The methodological manual "reading 1", on the other hand, focuses on the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for the pedagogical activity of the teacher in teaching 1st grade "reading", and notes that students should independently read and speak small texts, memorize small poetic passages, and master the skills of conscious reading unfamiliar texts. The manual provides separate recommendations for working on artistic text, and also provides sample lesson developments for reading lessons, advanced pedagogical methods used in lessons, exercises and samples of didactic games.

In the guide "reading 2", the authors described the necessary information about the convenient ways and methods of organizing 2nd grade reading classes. It contains a sample technological map of reading lessons, as well as sample lesson developments based on a total of 42 advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies on this basis. While the authors set out recommendations for the organization of reading classes, they tried to

bring more comprehensive information about the types of reading in primary classes and methods of applying advanced pedagogical technologies in classes.

Multimedia applications of methodological manuals for teachers highlighted above serve as an interactive electronic information and educational resource, which has additional materials that serve to effectively master the teaching science “reading” in elementary grades with the help of information and communication technologies, help students to receive independent education, enrich the main content of the academic discipline. It is also important that special attention is paid to working on text in these multimedia applications.

The state educational standard and curriculum of general Secondary Education states that the understanding, fluency, tactility of oral, monological and dialogical speech of students, understanding the content of the text, avoiding repetition of words, ensuring logical consistency in the statement of their thoughts in written and oral form, achieving speech purity and accuracy are important requirements.

Sections in the primary-grade native language program are given in the form of “teaching literacy and speech cultivation”, “phonetics, grammar, correct writing and speech cultivation”, “classroom, extracurricular reading and speech cultivation” [6].

The program for the first grade also emphasizes the need to conduct exercises aimed at developing speech organs to grow children's oral speech, develop speech skills, improve the correct pronunciation of words, correct certain shortcomings in children's speech, enrich the vocabulary, compose a small story, retell, and in the process achieve a clear, complete and emotional, consistent and meaningful speech.

” The main part of the reading lessons is allocated to reading the work and working on the text, ” the harmonized program of the 1st Grade [7] says. In the process of working on the text, it is necessary to get answers from the reader to the questions posed by the teacher on the works and the questions posed in the textbook, determine the subject circle of the work, compare the title with the main thought in the work, retell the full content of the work or teach to comment on the work, disassemble the work, , important aspects such as teaching certain words in the text to find meaningless, contradictory meanings are also highlighted in this program.

”Program for the second grade ” [8]at the time of the second grade reading classes of Secondary Schools, special attention should be paid to the mental,

ITALY

ITALY

moral upbringing of children, manners of treatment, fluency and elegance of their speech, to carry out the simplest work of analyzing the artistic text in reading lessons and to slowly teach them to perform complex tasks.

With the help of a teacher, the ability to divide the text into parts, choose titles for them, determine the main content of the text, analyze words and phrases describing the participants in the text, landscapes of nature, and draw up an oral story with the participation of these words, distinguish fairy tales, poems, stories according to genre characteristics is one of the main requirements

It seems that in the current DTS and native language program of primary classes, targeted work on speech growth is also prescribed, and they are given in consistency.

References:

1. Aminova F. H. O'quvchilarni muloqot matni yaratishga o'rgatishning didaktik asoslari: Ped. fan. nomz. ...dis. avtoref. – T.: O'zPFITI. 2007. – 22 b.
2. Aslonova O.P. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tafakkur tezligini shakllantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari: Ped. fanl. bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD). ... diss. avtoref. – QarDU. 2020. – 49 b.
3. Asqarova M., Matchonov S., Qodirova F., G'ulomova X., Boymatova A., Bozorova M., Muhamedova D. O'zbek tili mashg'ulotlarida nutq o'stirish. – T.: TDPU, 2000. – 58 b.
4. Babaeva D.R. Nutq o'stirish metodikasi (tevarak-atrofnii o'rganish misolida) – T.: Fan va texnologiya, 2009. – 128 b.
5. Bakieva X.S. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida mustaqil ta'lim orqali nutq va tafakkurni rivojlantirish metodikasi: Ped. fanl. bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD). ... diss. avtoref. – TDPU. 2019. – 47 b.
6. Bekniyazova N. Ta'lim qoraqalpoq tilida olib boriladigan maktablarning boshlang'ich sinflarida o'quvchilar so'z boyligini oshirish: Ped. fan. nomz. ...diss. avtoref. – T.: 1998. – 22 b.
7. Bekniyazova N. Boshlang'ich sinflar ona tili darslarida o'quvchilarga matn yaratishni o'rgatish metodikasi (ta'lim o'zbek va qoraqalpoq tillarida olib boriladigan maktablar misolida): Monografiya. – T.: Fan va texnologiyalar, 2012. – 160 b.
8. Ziyodova T. Matn yaratish texnologiyasi. – T.: Fan, 2007.– 144 b.
9. Ziyadova T.U. Ona tili ta'limi jarayonida o'quvchilarning so'z boyligini oshirish: Ped. fan. nomz. ...dis. avtoref. – T.: TDPI. 1995.– 19 b.

